

A Study of Clinical and Pathological Correlations in Hemodialysis Patients with Chronic Kidney DiseaseAkshi Patel¹, Yogesh Patel², Sachin Patel³^{1,3}Assistant Professor, Department of Pathology, Nootan Medical College and Research Centre, Visnagar, Gujarat, India²Assistant Professor, Department of Respiratory Medicine, Nootan Medical College and Research Centre, Visnagar, Gujarat, India

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Conflict of interest: Nil

Abstract:**Background and Aim:** Chronic Kidney Disease (CKD) represents a significant global health challenge, linked to heightened rates of morbidity and mortality. The primary aim of this study is to assess the clinical manifestations and different pathological changes in patients with chronic kidney disease undergoing haemodialysis. It also seeks to compare and correlate various clinical and pathological parameters in these patients, with a particular focus on those with diabetic kidney disease.**Material and Methods:** A cross-sectional study was conducted in the Department of Pathology at a Tertiary Care Teaching Institute in India, involving 80 patients with chronic kidney disease (CKD). A structured questionnaire that underwent pre-testing was developed to gather clinical data and results from pathological investigations. All clinical data were meticulously documented and analysed in relation to different haematological and biochemical parameters.**Results:** Elevated blood pressure was observed in 60 patients (75%), while the remaining 20 patients (25%) exhibited a BP of 160 mmHg. Additionally, 10 out of the 60 patients (16.6%) had blood pressure readings ranging from 120 to 139 mmHg. The analysis revealed that patients with chronic kidney disease exhibited significantly reduced levels of RBC count, haemoglobin, hematocrit/PCV, and platelet count ($p < 0.05$) when compared to the average values observed in healthy adults.**Conclusion:** Chronic kidney disease (CKD) is linked to various abnormalities in haematological and biochemical parameters, highlighting the necessity for early investigation and intervention. Patients with Diabetic Kidney Disease (DKD) exhibit a higher level of risk when compared to those with Non-Diabetic Kidney Disease (NDKD).**Keywords:** Blood Pressure, Chronic Kidney Disease, Diabetic Kidney Disease, Hemodialysis.

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Introduction

Chronic kidney disease (CKD) represents a range of clinical and laboratory abnormalities characterised by a gradual and ongoing deterioration of kidney function. A systematic review of population-based studies worldwide reports a composite median prevalence of CKD in persons aged 30 years or older of 7.2%. [1] Chronic kidney disease significantly affects both morbidity and mortality rates. This condition is widespread among the adult population and poses a significant burden, particularly in developing countries such as India, where the cost of care can be exceptionally high. [2]

A recent study from Nephrology's Kidney Disease Data Centre has revealed an international prevalence rate of 17%. [3] Currently, diabetes and hypertension are responsible for 40–60% of chronic

kidney disease cases in India. [4] Elevated blood sugar levels in individuals with diabetes can lead to damage in small blood vessels across the body, particularly affecting the kidneys. Individuals living with diabetes are at an increased risk of experiencing elevated blood pressure and accelerated arterial hardening, both of which can contribute to the development of heart disease and vision problems. [5]

The pathological changes linked to disruptions in haematological and biochemical parameters are the primary contributors to morbidity and mortality among patients with chronic kidney disease (CKD). Normocytic Normochromic Anaemia (NNA) is a common type of anaemia observed in patients with chronic kidney disease (CKD). This condition arises from a deficiency in erythropoietin, along

with factors such as blood loss and a reduced lifespan of red blood cells. [6] Absolute IDA is characterized by a transferrin saturation (TSAT) of less than 20% and a ferritin level ranging from 100 to 500 ng/mL. [8] Increased levels of hepcidin are primarily responsible for functional iron deficiency. The primary causes linked to chronic kidney disease (CKD) are diabetes mellitus and hypertension. [7,8]

Chronic inflammation significantly contributes to the advancement of chronic kidney disease, as evidenced by elevated levels of inflammatory mediators linked to diminished renal function. [9] Platelet dysfunction frequently occurs in patients suffering from renal insufficiency. [10] Identifying and addressing these conditions at an early stage can enhance the quality of life for individuals with chronic kidney disease. The primary aim of this study is to assess the clinical symptoms and different pathological alterations in patients with chronic kidney disease undergoing haemodialysis. Additionally, it seeks to compare and correlate various clinical and pathological parameters in these patients, with a particular focus on those suffering from diabetic kidney disease.

Material and Methods

A cross-sectional study was conducted in the Department of Pathology at a Tertiary Care Teaching Institute in India, spanning a duration of one year. The research commenced following the approval of the Institutional Ethics Committee.

The study population comprised individuals diagnosed with chronic kidney disease who were undergoing maintenance haemodialysis. Individuals who declined to provide consent for a biopsy or presented with significant contraindications—including infection at the biopsy site, active renal or peri-renal infections, structural and anatomical abnormalities of the kidney, the presence of cysts and renal masses, having a solitary kidney, coagulopathy, and uncontrolled hypertension—were not included in the study. A total of 80 cases were incorporated into the study.

A structured questionnaire, which underwent pre-testing, was developed to gather clinical data and details from pathological investigations. Clinical data regarding the gender, age, underlying comorbid conditions for developing CKD, presenting complaints, individual's blood pressure and random blood sugar were recorded at the beginning of study. Various haematological and biochemical parameters were assessed, including RBC count, haemoglobin levels, hematocrit/PCV, RDW, red cell indices, WBC count, platelet count, peripheral blood smear analysis, ESR, iron studies, renal function tests, and serum potassium levels. Blood samples were gathered in an EDTA

anticoagulant tube for a range of haematological assessments, including RBC count, haemoglobin levels, packed cell volume (PCV), WBC count, and erythrocyte sedimentation rate (ESR), among others. Blood samples were obtained in plain tubes without anticoagulant for the purpose of biochemical investigations. The study examined haematological and biochemical parameters in patients with chronic kidney disease, comparing them to normal control values, with a particular focus on those with diabetic chronic kidney disease.

Statistical analysis

The collected data was organised and input into a spreadsheet application (Microsoft Excel 2019) before being transferred to the data editor interface of SPSS version 19 (SPSS Inc., Chicago, Illinois, USA). Quantitative variables were characterised by their means and standard deviations or by their medians and interquartile ranges, depending on the distribution observed. Qualitative variables were reported as counts and percentages. In all analyses conducted, a confidence level of 95% and a significance level of 5% were established.

Results

In our research involving 80 patients with chronic kidney disease receiving haemodialysis, a significant majority, 70 patients (87.5%), were male, while only 10 patients (12.5%) were female. The age of the patients varied between 31 and 75 years. The highest prevalence of chronic kidney disease (CKD) was observed in the age group of 40 to 49 years, accounting for 67.5% of cases. This was followed by individuals aged 51 to 60 years at 16.25%, while those in the 31 to 40 years and 61 to 75 years age brackets each represented 6.25% of the total cases (Table 1).

In our study, we found common co-morbid conditions leading to CKD were hypertension combined with diabetes in 33 patients accounting for (41.25%), followed by diabetes in 18 patients (22.5%), hypertension in 16 patients (20%), coronary artery disease in 6 patients and chronic obstructive pulmonary disease in 7 patients comprising for 7.5 and 8.5% each (Table 2). In patients with chronic kidney disease receiving haemodialysis, the predominant clinical manifestation observed was pedal oedema. This was closely followed by symptoms such as headache, nausea and vomiting, fever, pruritus, chest pain, and breathlessness. In this study, systolic blood pressure measurements were taken from all 80 patients with chronic kidney disease at the outset, utilising a sphygmomanometer applied to the brachial artery through the auscultatory technique. In a recent assessment, elevated blood pressure was observed in 60 patients, accounting for 75% of the cohort. The remaining 20 patients,

or 25%, exhibited blood pressure readings of 160 mmHg, while 10 out of the 60 patients, representing 16.6%, had blood pressure levels ranging from 120 to 139 mmHg. Out of 80 patients with chronic kidney disease, 56 were previously diagnosed with diabetes. The findings regarding the impact of Chronic Kidney Disease on haematological and biochemical parameters are detailed in Table 3. The data indicates that patients with CKD exhibited significantly lower levels of RBC count, haemoglobin, hematocrit/PCV, and platelet count ($p < 0.05$) when compared to the average control values observed in healthy adults.

In a study involving 80 patients with chronic kidney disease (CKD), a significant 90% were found to be anaemic. This was determined by haemoglobin levels falling below 12.5 gm/dl in females and 13 gm/dl in males, or packed cell volume (PCV) levels below 35% in females and 40% in males. Notably, most of these patients were classified as having moderate anaemia. In the analysis of peripheral smears, Normocytic Normochromic Anaemia emerged as the predominant morphology, observed in 75% of cases. Additionally, the red cell distribution width (RDW) and other red cell indices remained within normal limits for these patients. In the remaining 25% of patients, the peripheral blood smear revealed Microcytic Hypochromic Anaemia as the predominant morphological type. Additionally, there was an increase in RDW, while MCV, MCH, and MCHC were observed to be at the lower limits of the normal range. Iron studies conducted indicated that 65% of CKD patients, specifically 52

out of 80, exhibited reduced serum ferritin levels. In our study, it was observed that serum iron, transferrin saturation, and total iron binding capacity were within normal limits for 44 out of 80 (55%) of the chronic kidney disease patients. The current study revealed that iron deficiency anaemia is more common than functional iron deficiency in patients with chronic kidney disease (CKD). Tests assessing renal function indicated markedly increased levels of serum creatinine and blood urea in patients with chronic kidney disease when compared to normal controls ($p < 0.05$). A mild elevation in serum potassium levels was observed in the majority of chronic kidney disease patients, with 50 out of 80 (62.5%) exhibiting this condition, while the remaining 30 out of 80 patients (37.5%) had levels within the normal range.

Our research revealed a notable decrease in red blood cell count, haemoglobin levels, and hematocrit/PCV among patients with diabetic kidney disease when contrasted with those without the condition. Interestingly, the platelet count observed in patients with diabetic kidney disease (DKD) and those without (NDKD) revealed no significant differences. Our study presents compelling evidence suggesting a link between inflammation and diabetes, as indicated by significantly elevated total White Blood Cell counts and ESR in patients with Diabetic Kidney Disease (DKD) compared to those without (NDKD). The majority of patients with diabetic kidney disease exhibited a significant rise in chronic inflammatory cells, including lymphocytes and monocytes.

Table 1: Age and gender distribution of CKD patients

Age (Years)	Males	Females	Total
30-39	7	1	8 (10)
40-49	49	5	54 (67.5)
50-59	10	3	13 (16.25)
60-75	4	1	5 (6.25)
total	70	10	80

Table 2: Distribution of CKD patients with underlying co-morbidities

Co-morbidities	Number	Percentage (%)
Diabetes	18	22.5
Hypertension	16	20
Hypertension + Diabetes	33	41.25
Coronary artery disease	6	7.5
COPD	7	8.75

Table 3: Comparison of haematological and biochemical parameters between diabetic CKD patients (DKD) and non-diabetic CKD patients (NDKD)

Variables	DKD patients (Mean±SD)	NDKD patients (Mean±SD)	P value
RBC count (million/cumm)	2.25±0.26	3.90±0.77	0.002*
Hemoglobin (gm/dl)	7.18±1.10	11.48±2.11	0.01*
PCV/Hematocrit (%)	22.50±5.90	31.60±3.90	0.05*
Platelet count (lakhs/cumm)	1799.45±12500.70	1897.30±11550.48	0.22
MCV (femtoliter)	81.97±7.22	81.10±5.34	0.52
MCH (picograms)	26.98±4.12	27.89±3.10	0.9
MCHC (gm/dl)	32.48±5.11	33.26±4.12	0.12
WBC count (per microliter)	16410.89±4112.14	11788.30±3100.90	0.003*
ESR (mm/hr)	32.65±11.23	27.48±8.11	0.05*
Total serum iron (mcg/dL)	98.99±19.40	99.63±27.10	0.22
Serum Ferritin (mcg/L)	23.50±60.11	28.11±59.65	0.39
Serum Creatinine (mg/dL)	8.20±3.5	7.77±2.90	0.36
Blood Urea(mg/dL)	125.32±30.47	119.65±28.42	0.47
Serum Potassium (mmol/L)	6.20±1.11	5.99±1.50	0.65

* Indicate statistically significance at $p \leq 0.05$

Discussion

In the present study, the mean age of CKD patients was 50 years which is higher compared to studies done by Low J et al. [11] and Rasheed N et al [12] which showed mean age of 41 years and 31.3 years respectively. In our study, we observed that male patients with chronic kidney disease exhibited a significantly higher prevalence compared to their female counterparts within the same age group. This aligns with findings reported by Ferdinand et al. [13]

The current study reveals that the most prevalent comorbidity associated with chronic kidney disease (CKD) is the combination of hypertension and diabetes, observed in the majority of patients. This is followed by diabetes mellitus as a significant factor among CKD patients. This aligns with the findings of studies conducted by Bhatta S et al [14] and George SV et al [15]. Chinwuba et al [5] reported that the prevalence of hypertension and diabetes mellitus was lower compared to chronic glomerulonephritis among CKD patients in their study. A statistically significant association has been observed between low red blood cell count and reduced haematocrit levels in patients with chronic kidney disease, with a p-value of less than 0.05 when compared to the normal adult population. The results of this research align with the study conducted by Alghythan A K et al. [17] and Al-Ageel N et al. [18] The severity of renal disease in patients with chronic kidney disease (CKD) correlates with the progression of anaemia. [19]

Our research revealed notably lower haemoglobin levels and platelet counts in patients with chronic kidney disease when compared to the normal adult population, aligning with the findings of Habib A et al. [20] Suresh M and colleagues [21], along with Turedi S and their team. [22] Several factors

contribute to the reduced red blood cell counts and haematocrit levels observed in patients with chronic kidney disease. These include impaired synthesis of erythropoietin, a shortened lifespan of red blood cells, and suppressed erythropoiesis in the bone marrow, all of which ultimately lead to a decrease in haemoglobin concentration. [23,24] The red cell indices observed in our study revealed no significant differences between patients with chronic kidney disease (CKD) and healthy individuals. This aligns with findings from research conducted by Alghythan A K et al. and Ferdinand et al., indicating that normocytic normochromic anaemia is the predominant morphological type of anaemia observed in CKD patients. Burr cells tend to rise in number as uremia worsens, while the presence of fragmented red blood cells indicates a potential haemolytic issue. This could stem from factors such as reduced adenosine triphosphatase activity in the red blood cell membrane, shortened red cell lifespan in uremia, or exposure to harmful substances in the dialysate, including copper, nitrates, and formaldehyde. [25] Diebold, M et al. [26] found a notable decrease in serum iron and serum ferritin levels among patients with chronic renal failure who were receiving haemodialysis. In a study conducted in Turkey, Tekce H et al. [27] found that patients with end-stage renal disease exhibited low levels of transferrin. Regular assessment of iron levels is essential for the effective management of iron deficiency anaemia in patients with chronic kidney disease. The current research demonstrated elevated white blood cell counts, characterized by absolute lymphocytosis and monocytosis, aligning with findings from Reddan DN et al. and Alghythan et al. [17] The elevated occurrence of latent or secondary infections in these patients could be a contributing factor.

The current study revealed a notable link between increased blood urea levels in patients with chronic kidney disease and those in healthy adults. This finding aligns with the results of studies conducted by Haythem A et al. [28] and Ali S et al. [29] in India. Chronic renal disease leads to an irreversible decline in kidney function, causing the accumulation of nitrogenous waste products, which manifests as elevated levels of blood urea nitrogen and nonprotein nitrogen. Elevated serum creatinine levels showed a strong correlation with patients suffering from chronic kidney disease. Considering these findings, it is suggested that renal damage might not correlate with changes in renal functions or other indicators like albuminuria during the early stages. Patients in this study did not undergo microalbuminuria estimation that could have investigated lower cutoff values of proteinuria. Identifying CKDu at an early stage presents significant challenges. Given that many cases of renal pathology are identified with only slight increases in serum creatinine and +2 albuminuria, it is crucial to investigate alternative biomarkers for early detection of chronic kidney disease of unknown aetiology (CKDu). Traditional renal parameters may fall short in identifying the disease at its onset. The most prevalent form of anaemia observed in patients with diabetic kidney disease (DKD) is morphologically normocytic normochromic anaemia, a finding that aligns with the research conducted by Taderegew M M et al. Our study found that patients with diabetic kidney disease exhibited significantly higher white blood cell counts and erythrocyte sedimentation rates. This suggests a potential link between elevated blood sugar levels and increased inflammatory activity in individuals suffering from this condition.

Conclusion

CKD is associated with abnormalities in different haematological and biochemical parameters that requires early investigation and treatment. Also, Diabetic Kidney Disease patients (DKD) show greater degree of risk compared to Non-Diabetic Kidney Disease (NDKD) patients. Normocytic normochromic anemia was the commonest morphology seen in both DKD and NDKD patients.

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